

EXPLORING THE PERCEPTIONS OF CAREER SUSTAINABILITY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF CAREER ADAPTABILITY AND THE MODERATING ROLE OF FAMILY ROLE

Muhammad Adeel Abid^{*1}, Muhammad Mohsin², Ishna Arshad³, Kinza Iman⁴,
Rafia Rasheed⁵, Esha Noor⁶

^{*1,2}Ph. D Scholar Lecturer Department of Management and Administrative Sciences University of Narowal,
Punjab, Pakistan

^{3,4,5,6}Research Scholar Faculty of Business and Management Sciences University of Narowal, Pakistan

¹adeel.abid@uon.edu.pk, ²muhammad.mohsin@uon.edu.pk, ³ishnaarshad15122001@gmail.com,
⁴kinzaiman340@gmail.com, ⁵rafiaarasheed98@gmail.com, ⁶eshanoor004@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Adeel Abid

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20508488>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
29 May, 2025	29 June, 2025	12 July, 2025	19 July, 2025

ABSTRACT

Purpose: Recently, sustainability studies have been a hot topic due to the renewed interest in the concept and the improvements in its performances and measures. The study aims to assess the perception of career sustainability among university students by analyzing hope, future work self, academic self-efficacy, and life satisfaction while mediating the relationship of career adaptability and family role as moderators. A Google-based survey investigated the university students' understanding of career sustainability. 251 useable responses through non-probability purposive sampling were used for the data analysis. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was applied for data analysis. According to the findings, hope, future work self, academic self-efficacy, and life satisfaction was positively connected to career sustainability, with the family role as a moderator regulating career adaptability. This study makes a valuable contribution to the existing body of research concerning career sustainability.

Keywords: Hope (HOP), Career Adaptability (CA), Future Work Self (FWS), Family Role (FR), Life Satisfaction (LS), Career Sustainability (CS), Academic Self-efficacy (ASE).

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the dynamic and uncertain nature of the economic landscape has led to a growing emphasis on career sustainability among people, organizations, and society (Lawrence, Hall, Arthur, De Vos, & Van der Heijden, 2015). Recently published studies have attempted to look at factors that influence career sustainability. De Vos, Van der Heijden, and Akkermans (2020) proposed that "sequences of career experiences reflected through a variety of patterns of continuity over time, thereby crossing several social spaces, characterized by individual agency, herewith providing meaning to the individual."

Maintaining health, happiness, and performance throughout their careers has thus become a crucial topic of concern. The new formulation of career sustainability indicators and dimensions has emerged as a critical area of research (De Vos et al., 2020).

Moreover, previous research on the subject of career sustainability has used qualitative methodology, as shown by the work of (van den Groenendaal et al., 2022). Alternatively, previous research has used a restricted set of factors to evaluate career sustainability, with (Tordera, Peiro, Ayala, Villajos, & Truxillo, 2020) being a

notable exception. While qualitative studies have significantly contributed to the initial understanding of sustainable careers, more empirical research is necessary to advance the growing body of literature in this field (De Vos et al., 2020). To contribute to this area, the study assesses the relationship among different variables. There are a lot of factors that affect the career sustainability of fresh and even post-graduate students. So, this study focuses on filling this gap by regulating career adaptability. The research examines the perception of career sustainability among students and whether career adaptability mediates career sustainability via life satisfaction, hope, academic self-efficacy, and future work self. Either family role connected positively with career adaptability and career sustainability. Career adaptability is a psychological benefit in career growth. People must navigate professional instability and transition between career stages (Savickas, 2005). The present study investigated whether career adaptability attributes entirely or partially buffer their associations. The study showed how family role affects career sustainability. It also examines whether family role moderates career sustainability and career adaptability association. There was limited data for family role where the associations would be established. So, this research is novel in its applicability in terms of using family role as a moderator. Moreover, the study has the potential to provide valuable insights by investigating the influence of family roles on career sustainability. Finally, this study incorporates career construction theory for successful career integration. This project may allow future researchers to study particular mechanisms as the conceptual frameworks discuss longevity. Our study would also help students achieve career sustainability.

Literature Review

The career construction theory collects “psychosocial abilities that condition self-regulation in coping with the tasks, transitions, and traumas” (Hirschi, Herrmann, & Keller, 2015). It involves adapting responses and strategies people employ to deal with the challenges of professional advancement and changing workplace and personal situations (Hirschi et al., 2015). It is considered crucial for people to effectively navigate professional

instability and successfully move between different career stages (Savickas, 2005). The word “sustainability” is employed in research to manage the present modes in the exterior world, which intimidate careers (Greenhaus & Kossek, 2014). A career without self-knowledge might be disastrous since one may obtain a goal that does not reflect one’s true inclinations. In this case, a person crashes for a sustained win that prevents them from meeting realistic goals (De Hauw & Greenhaus, 2015). Recently, a survey by Gallup found that the loss of jobs, increased stress, and decreased engagement among working professionals negatively impact the economy by US\$8.1 trillion annually (Gallup, 2022).

Hope with Career Adaptability and Career Sustainability

Hope is traced as “the perceived capacity to derive pathways to desired goals and motivate oneself via agency thinking to use those pathways” (Snyder, 2002). Hope was seen as an emotive variable that sustained the activity and influenced notions and behaviours (Scioli et al., 1997). In a study conducted by Santilli, Nota, Ginevra, and Soresi (2014), those who see themselves as capable of building their future career intentions and enduring shifts in careers and challenging positions have more career adaptability. In addition to hope, in light of recent years’ worth of global changes, threats, and the need to take action in support of sustainable development (Watts, Diemer, & Voight, 2011). Thus on the basis of above literature we hypothesized that:

H1: Hope positively impacts career adaptability

H2: Hope positively impacts career sustainability

Future Work Self with Career Adaptability and Career Sustainability

Future work self is interpreted as the self-concept that inspires professional activities and includes future ambitions for work life (Strauss, Griffin, & Parker, 2012). As mentioned in past research, developing dynamic skills and professional strategy are closely related to one’s future employment (Taber & Blankemeyer, 2015) and predict increased chances of career sustainability. Future work-self might be conceptualized as adaptive preparedness, as it pertains to individuals’ forward-thinking perspective and inclination to engage in proactive career-related actions (Ginevra, Pallini, Vecchio, Nota, &

Soresi, 2016; Johnston, 2018). Thus, we proposed that:

H3: Future work self positively impacts career adaptability

H4: Future work self positively impacts career sustainability

Academic Self-Efficacy with Career Adaptability and Career Sustainability

One's belief in the capacity to carry out specific tasks or acquire particular skills is called self-efficacy (Bandura, 1978). Higher academic self-efficacy is linked positively to exceptional educational outcomes and positive learning-related feelings, as in prior research (Akanni & Oduaran, 2018; Zeinalipour, 2021). Career adaptability has mainly focused on responses (Hirschi et al., 2015) and academic responses (Avram, Burtaverde, & Zanfirescu, 2019; Tolentino et al., 2014; Wilkins-Yel, Roach, Tracey, & Yel, 2018). High academic self-efficacy in students' career are more engaged, driven, and confident that they can complete the work and overcome hurdles, which enhances their satisfaction and success in life. Even if a difficulty arose unexpectedly, students with new career skills or confidence can achieve career sustainability better. Thus, we proposed that:

H5: Academic self-efficacy positively impacts career adaptability

H6: Academic self-efficacy positively impacts career sustainability

Life Satisfaction with Career Adaptability and Career Sustainability

Prior studies have revealed that a critical envisage of life satisfaction in young adults is the process of making judgments, how individuals assess the worth of their lives according to their unique standards, as outlined (Pavot & Diener, 1993). According to Santilli et al. (2014), young individuals experience increased satisfaction when they possess career-oriented aspirations and a clear sense of direction in their professional endeavours. Individuals who experience elevated levels of life satisfaction within their chosen profession tend to exhibit greater engagement and motivation. This engagement in a career and motivation subsequently contribute to increased happiness and the potential for a prolonged career, boosting overall career sustainability. Thus we proposed:

H7: Life satisfaction positively impacts career adaptability

H8: Life satisfaction positively impacts a sustainable career

Mediating Role of Career Adaptability with Hope, Future Work Self, Academic Self-Efficacy, and Life Satisfaction

According to Staats (1989), hope may include two distinct elements. The first component is cognitive, about the individual's beliefs and expectations about the possibility of a future event. Students who may shift have more significant consequences for their future professional development and handle complex academic tasks assume that advanced education is essential for success in any sector (Avram et al., 2019). Prior research on career adaptability has mainly focused on career responses (Hirschi et al., 2015) and academics (Avram et al., 2019; Wilkins-Yel et al., 2018). Higher academic self-efficacy promotes career sustainability. Life satisfaction strongly indicates career adaptability (Hirschi, 2009). This motivation increases happiness and the potential for carrying a career and promotes overall career sustainability. Thus we proposed that:

H9: Career adaptability mediates the relationship between hope and career sustainability

H10: Career adaptability mediates the relationship between future work self and career sustainability

H11: Career adaptability mediates the relationship between academic self-efficacy and career sustainability

H12: Career adaptability mediates the relationship between life satisfaction and career sustainability

Relationship between Career Adaptability and Career Sustainability

According to Savickas and Porfeli (2012), career adaptability is the psychological resource for coping with present and future career-related responsibilities, changes, and painful events. Career sustainability pertains to an individual's capacity to maintain and enhance their career prospects and well-being in the face of evolving work demands and opportunities. Career adaptability enables people to modify their career objectives, discover novel avenues, and acquire

fresh expertise to reinforce their career sustainability. The relationship between career adaptability and the inclination to address systematic obstacles to achieve sustainable growth is positively associated with the tendency to invest in higher education driven by hope (Di Maggio, Santilli, Ginevra, Nota, & Soresi, 2018). Consequently, career adaptability and career sustainability are interconnected. Thus we proposed:

Hypothesis 13: Career adaptability has a relationship with career sustainability.

The Moderating Effect of Family Role:

A family role is a person’s relationships, expectations, and obligations within the family and the larger society are shaped. Family duties may differ based on the family’s composition, cultural background, and even the personality

traits of its members. The foundation of our research revolved around the belief that family influence on wealth, parents’ level of education, engagement in work, and academic satisfaction are fundamental components (Young, 1983). Participation of parents in their children’s education and the development of their children’s careers is of utmost importance. They can contribute significantly by assisting their children in assessing their aptitude, exploring their interests, providing encouragement to pursue their aspirations, and imparting knowledge about various career options for adapting a career. Motivation and engagement with a career promote career sustainability. Thus we proposed:

H14: Family role moderated the relationship between career adaptability and career sustainability.

Conceptual Framework:

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Methodology

Procedures

A Google-based survey was employed for data collection from February 2023 to May 2023. Information was gathered from various public sector university students from Pakistan. The total survey was completed by sending 300 questionnaires, from which 251 were returned with valid response rates randomly selected for data collection via software (Zeng et al., 2022). This study was deductive, and non-probability purposive sampling was applied to select respondents.

Measures

This work used scaled questionnaires to acquire data. We used a five-point Likert scale, 1 strongly disagree and 5 strongly agree. Hope was measured using scale developed by (Chen, Shen, & Li, 2009) with 6-item, Future work self-scale created by (Strauss et al., 2012) was assessed by 5-items, Academic Self-efficacy was measured with 5 items developed by (Liang, 2000; Pintrich & De Groot, 1990), Life satisfaction is measured with 2 items created by (Zhang, Ligu, & Xue, 2004), Career Adaptability scale is measured with 2 items

developed by (Savickas & Porfeli, 2012). Career sustainability is measured with 3 items developed by (Diener, Suh, Lucas, & Smith, 1999; Williams & Anderson, 1991) and family role is measured with 6 items developed by (Uddin & Bhuiyan, 2019).

Data Analysis:

This study tested direct and indirect correlation hypotheses using Smart PLS 3.0. Since PLS-SEM has found widespread application in studies of management (Suen, Chen, & Lu, 2019; Yang & Lin, 2014). We employed it to test and evaluate the structural model. Using it clarifies complex

interactions between measurable and un-measurable components. Cronbach’s alpha and CR (composite reliability) determined reliability. Data was taken from Google Forms and modified in Excel. After being dragged into PLS-SEM, it analyzes the descriptive status of variables N=251 and computes all their dimensions to create a calculated variable. Demographic variables like gender, income, education, and living status were tested. It examined how all variables affected career sustainability. Mediation and moderation analysis were validated with an accuracy of 95% using PLS-SEM on 5000 bootstrap samples.

Table 1: Respondent Profile

Demo	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	77	30.7
	Female	174	69.3
Age	Below18	22	8.8
	19 to 30	216	86.1
	30 to 40	9	3.6
	40 & above	4	1.6
Academic Qualification	Bachelors	189	75.3
	Masters	47	18.7
	M.Phil. & above	15	6.0
Current Status	Full time	194	77.3
	Weekend	57	22.7
Living Status	Parents	159	63.3
	Grand Parents	2	0.8
	Apartment	8	3.2
	Hostel	26	10.4
	Joint Family	56	22.3
Monthly Income	Below 10k	139	55.4
	10k to 20k	41	16.3
	20k to 30k	27	10.8
	30k to above	44	17.5

The 30.7% of 251 survey respondents were male, and 69.3% were female. About 8.8% of persons were under 18, 86.1% were 19 to 30, 3.6% were 30 to 40, and 1.6% were over 40. Academically, 75.3% were bachelors, 18% masters, and 6% M.Phil or higher. Currently, 77.3% of people attend full-time classes, and 22.7% attend weekend sessions. 63.3% lived with parents, 0.8% with grandparents, 3.2% in apartments, 10.4% in hostels, and 22.3% in joint families. Monthly income results: 55.4% had less than

10k, 16.3% had 10k to 20k, 10.8% had 20k to 30k, and 17.5% had 30k+.

Measurement Model Assessment

Convergent validity:

In this case, the convergent and discriminant validity of the measurement model is evaluated via “confirmatory factor analysis”. How reliable a system is can be determined by factor loading, Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) (Sarstedt et al., 2021). The CR is expected to be greater than

0.70, the AVE greater than 0.5, and the Cronbach's alpha higher than 0.7. The loadings of the factors ought to be more than 0.5.

Table 2: Convergent validity

Constructs	items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
Academic Self-efficacy	ASE1	0.860	0.863	0.853	0.674
	ASE2	0.755			
	ASE3	0.673			
	ASE4	0.631			
	ASE5	0.735			
Career Adaptability	CA1	0.892	0.847	0.848	0.737
	CA2	0.823			
Career Sustainability	CS1	0.902	0.937	0.937	0.832
	CS2	0.931			
	CS3	0.904			
Family Role	FR1	0.742	0.907	0.907	0.619
	FR2	0.862			
	FR3	0.718			
	FR4	0.791			
	FR5	0.729			
	FR6	0.865			
Future Work Self	FWS2	0.723	0.813	0.812	0.52
	FWS3	0.793			
	FWS4	0.662			
	FWS5	0.700			
	HOP1	0.697			
HOP2	0.904				
HOP3	0.765				
HOP4	0.742				
HOP5	0.469				
HOP6	0.628				
Life satisfaction	LS1	0.815	0.886	0.893	0.808
	LS2	0.976			

The instruments' consistency (as measured by composite reliability), discriminant validity (as measured by cross-loadings and Fornell-Larcker criteria, HTMT Ratio), and convergent validity (as measured by average variance extracted) were all evaluated using CFA. Table 2 displays the convergent validity, displaying AVE values for all latent components that are more than the 0.5 criterion, ranging from 0.509 to 0.832. If the latent construct's AVE was more than 0.5, it explained more than 50% of the variance in its indicators.

Table 2 provides findings of the measurement model. It employed parameter estimates and statistical significance, and the results indicated that all significant constructions including future work self, family role, hope, career adaptability,

life satisfaction, career sustainability, and academic self-efficacy were legitimate indicators of their respective constructs.

Discriminant Validity

The discriminant validity was calculated using two different metrics. The Fornell-Larcker criteria and cross-loadings had a role. Fornell and Larcker (1981) proposed criteria to determine whether or not a latent construct in a structural model has more significant variance with its indicators than other latent constructs. According to this norm, the off-diagonal values should be higher in association with each construct than the diagonal values are with the squared root of the AVE (Joseph F, 2016). Table 3 displays the constructs' discriminant validity of fornell- larker criteria.

The square root of the AVE values was more robust than other correlation values among the latent variables in Table 3, demonstrating that many of the model's components fit into different categories. A novel variance-based discriminant validity measure for structural equation models was developed by (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Thus, Henseler et al. (2015) introduced "the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations" to assess discriminant validity. The HTMT ratio may be used for either a criterion-based or analytical evaluation of the validity of the discriminant (Henseler et al.,

2015). (Kline, 2011); Watson et al. (1995) proposed a suitable HTMT ratio in the initial method is below 0.85. or 0.90 by (Gold, Malhotra, & Segars, 2001) to be considered acceptable. A confidence interval of one suggests that the test result lacks discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015), which leads to our second analysis phase. The first criteria were used to measure discriminant validity in this study. Table 4 shows that all constructs cleared the HTMT 0.90 criteria (Gold et al., 2001). Table 5 demonstrates factors loadings and figure 2 shows the results of measurement model assessment.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker)

	ASE	CA	CS	FR	FWS	HOP	LS
ASE	0.735						
CA	0.541	0.858					
CS	0.438	0.525	0.902				
FR	0.649	0.89	0.559	0.787			
FWS	0.852	0.681	0.555	0.674	0.721		
HOP	0.622	0.586	0.304	0.512	0.722	0.714	
LS	0.454	0.868	0.393	0.743	0.575	0.399	0.899

Table 4: Discriminant Validity (HTMT Ratio)

ASE	CA	CS	FM	FWS	HOP	LS
ASE						
CA	0.531					
CS	0.432	0.524				
FR	0.641	0.892	0.558			
FWS	0.833	0.68	0.557	0.674		
HOP	0.621	0.587	0.315	0.512	0.731	
LS	0.448	0.87	0.395	0.747	0.577	0.400

Table 5: Cross loadings

	ASE	CA	CS	FR	FWS	HOP	LS
ASE1	0.860	0.465	0.38	0.52	0.798	0.514	0.405
ASE2	0.755	0.408	0.214	0.462	0.552	0.437	0.319
ASE3	0.673	0.364	0.315	0.48	0.588	0.466	0.317
ASE4	0.631	0.341	0.32	0.44	0.545	0.433	0.319
ASE5	0.735	0.397	0.382	0.485	0.622	0.435	0.304
CA1	0.456	0.892	0.492	0.767	0.592	0.484	0.811
CA2	0.473	0.823	0.406	0.762	0.577	0.525	0.675
CS1	0.37	0.47	0.902	0.506	0.506	0.277	0.367
CS2	0.398	0.492	0.931	0.516	0.519	0.284	0.368
CS3	0.431	0.473	0.904	0.506	0.493	0.272	0.339
FR1	0.456	0.667	0.415	0.742	0.527	0.408	0.505
FR2	0.461	0.769	0.482	0.862	0.524	0.463	0.638
FR3	0.49	0.706	0.401	0.718	0.49	0.473	0.61
FR4	0.593	0.731	0.442	0.791	0.596	0.415	0.595
FR5	0.497	0.615	0.408	0.729	0.477	0.322	0.522
FR6	0.569	0.71	0.483	0.865	0.569	0.345	0.633

FWS2	0.613	0.492	0.441	0.49	0.723	0.604	0.419
FWS3	0.617	0.54	0.363	0.504	0.793	0.566	0.456
FWS4	0.606	0.451	0.411	0.448	0.662	0.423	0.37
FWS5	0.626	0.477	0.394	0.502	0.700	0.482	0.41
HOP1	0.405	0.409	0.163	0.345	0.537	0.697	0.29
HOP2	0.502	0.53	0.243	0.439	0.599	0.904	0.358
HOP3	0.501	0.448	0.207	0.415	0.54	0.765	0.314
HOP4	0.47	0.435	0.225	0.423	0.515	0.742	0.291
HOP5	0.364	0.275	0.233	0.217	0.45	0.469	0.2
HOP6	0.413	0.368	0.258	0.309	0.451	0.628	0.228
LS1	0.377	0.707	0.327	0.619	0.485	0.326	0.815
LS2	0.437	0.847	0.377	0.714	0.548	0.388	0.976

First, we looked at how different items were loaded onto each other. According to, the standardized loading estimations ought to be at least 0.5, and preferably 0.7 (Joseph F Hair Jr, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2010). All the items for each variable are then 0.7 or higher,

which is ideal situation. Academic self-efficacy, career adaptability, career sustainability, family role, future work self, hope and life satisfaction are achieved by the standard of cross-loadings criteria.

Figure 2: Measurement Model Assessment

Structural Model (SEM):

After verifying the precision of the measuring model, the hypotheses were examined. The structural model was tested by utilizing the PLS-SEM technique and bootstrapping (Vinzi, Chin,

Henseler, & Wang, 2010). To begin evaluating the effectiveness of the structural model for prediction, the magnitude and significance of the route coefficient were calculated (Joseph F, 2016).

Path Analysis

Table 6: Direct Relations

		Beta	SD	T Values	P-Values	UL	LL	Decision
H1	H -> CA	0.198	0.058	3.389	0.009	1.701	0.319	Supported
H2	H -> CS	0.032	0.018	1.815	0.001	1.657	0.071	Supported

H3	FWS → CA	0.127	0.066	1.938	0.009	1.853	0.252	Supported
H4	FWS → CS	0.021	0.017	1.207	0.002	1.722	0.063	Supported
H5	ASE → CA	0.013	0.062	0.215	0.001	1.831	0.138	Supported
H6	ASE → CS	0.002	0.011	0.198	0.019	1.943	0.026	Supported
H7	LS → CA	0.625	0.045	1.019	0.032	1.656	0.708	Supported
H8	LS → CS	0.101	0.049	2.048	0.002	1.704	0.197	Supported
H13	CA → CS	0.162	0.086	2.035	0.034	1.646	0.314	Supported

Direct Relationship-Path Analysis:

Joe F Hair Jr, Sarstedt, Hopkins, and Kuppelwieser (2014) claim that a statistically significant route supports the hypothesized causal link; if it does not, or if it shows signals in the other direction, it does not. Table 6 shows the bootstrapping findings. Here are all of the results: Table 6 showed the following results from PLS-SEM, which are H1 ($\beta = 0.198$, $t = 3.389$, $UL = 1.701$, $LL = 0.319$, $p = 0.009$), H2 ($\beta = 0.032$, $t = 1.815$, $p = 0.001$, $UL = 1.657$, $LL = 0.071$), H3 (β

$= 0.127$, $t = 1.938$, $UL = 1.853$, $LL = 0.252$, $p = 0.009$), H4 ($\beta = 0.021$, $t = 1.207$, $UL = 1.722$, $LL = 0.063$, $p = 0.002$), H5 ($\beta = 0.013$, $t = 0.215$, $UL = 1.831$, $LL = 0.138$, $p = 0.001$), H6 ($\beta = 0.002$, $t = 0.198$, $UL = 1.943$, $LL = 0.026$, $p = 0.019$), H7 ($\beta = 0.625$, $t = 1.019$, $UL = 1.656$, $LL = 0.708$, $p = 0.019$), H8 ($\beta = 0.101$, $t = 2.048$, $UL = 1.704$, $LL = 0.197$, $p = 0.002$) H13 ($\beta = 0.162$, $t = 2.035$, $UL = 1.646$, $LL = 0.314$, $p = 0.034$) proved as significant contributors and these hypothesis are accepted.

Table 7: Indirect Relation (Mediating effects)

		Beta	SD	T Values	P values	UL	LL	Decision
H9	H → CA → CS	0.032	0.018	1.815	0.001	1.843	0.071	Supported
H10	FWS → CA → CS	0.021	0.017	1.647	0.012	1.947	0.063	Supported
H11	ASE → CA → CS	0.002	0.011	1.718	0.019	1.745	0.026	Supported
H12	LS → CA → CS	0.101	0.049	2.048	0.021	1.654	0.197	Supported

Testing mediating effect of career adaptability:

In table 7, the mediation effect was examined following the testing of the relationships. There are numerous processes in evaluating this link, according to (Hayes, 2009).

As shown in Table 7, bootstrapping analysis revealed that the indirect impact of β is significant with t -values, which must be larger than 1.645. (Preacher & Hayes, 2008) also noted the indirect effect's 95% Boot CI of upper limit

and lower limit didn't cross 0 in the middle. As a result, the finding showed H9 ($\beta = 0.032$, $t = 1.815$, $p = 0.001$, $UL = 1.843$, $LL = 0.071$), H10 ($\beta = 0.021$, $t = 1.647$, $p = 0.012$, $UL = 1.947$, $LL = 0.063$), H11 ($\beta = 0.002$, $t = 1.718$, $p = 0.019$, $UL = 1.745$, $LL = 0.026$), H12 ($\beta = 0.101$; $t = 2.048$, $p = 0.021$, $UL = 1.654$, $LL = 0.197$) proved as significant contributors and these hypothesis are accepted.

Table 8: Indirect Effect (Moderating Role)

	Relationship	Beta	SD	T Values	P Values	LL	UL	Decision
H14	FR x CA → CS	0.051	0.042	1.764	0.035	1.243	0.035	Supported

Testing moderator effect of family role:

This study used the product indicator approach to investigate how family role affects the connection between career adaptability and career sustainability. The product indicator technique is considered appropriate when the

moderating construct is continuous in character, as stated by (Rigdon, Schumacker, Wothke, & Marcoulides, 1998). Additionally, (Henseler & Fassott, 2010) advised using the product terms strategy because its outcomes provided a more precise picture than other approaches. In

addition, Cohen (1988) recommendations were employed to estimate the magnitude of the interaction terms' effects. Referring to Table 8, the interaction term (FR*CA-> CS) for the Family Role supported with Career Adaptability and Career Sustainability was substantial ($\beta = 0.051$, $t = 1.764$, $p = 0.035$, $UL = 1.243$, $UL = 0.035$), as H14 is accepted.

Discussion:

Upon the premises of the career construction theory, we test the model test for career sustainability. The present study's findings carried positive correlations among Future work self, Academic self-efficacy, Hope and Life Satisfaction and tend to pursue their goals and have high career sustainability. Additionally, it found that career adaptability indirectly relates to career sustainability via Hope, future work self, Academic self-efficacy and Life satisfaction. According to (Gilman & Huebner, 2003) life satisfaction is a significant predictor of career sustainability. According to earlier research,; (Bi & Wang, 2021; Santilli, Marcionetti, Rochat, Rossier, & Nota, 2017), high Hope and a refined future work led to greater living satisfaction, ultimately achieving career sustainability in students.

Conclusion:

These results have several consequences, both theoretical and practical. This literature contributes that firstly, we relate career sustainability with a family role as a moderator. To connect them, we utilized the minimal data on the family role we studied. In the second place, we develop a conceptual model to learn how students think they can have a long and successful professional life. They are also more likely to achieve their goals. Techniques that enhance students' future work self and Hope can boost their well-being and academic self-efficacy, contributing to career sustainability. Institutions should provide career seminars or courses to pique further students' interest in developing a career and alleviate their concerns about the future. This may help people learn by accomplishing, gaining confidence, connecting with peers and teachers, and improving their local and global communities. Empirical research shows that family role can improve student career adaptability and sustainability. This adaptability

can handle volatile and ambiguous work environments. Parents should help children find career choices by discussing potential careers, nurturing passions and skills, and identifying professional development opportunities.

Future Recommendations and Limitations:

Firstly, we recommended gathering data through longitudinal research because it implies better findings in the future. Secondly, our data was limited to a few universities in Pakistan. In the future, other researchers may apply it in schools, colleges, and other educational institutes. Future studies may also use other variables, such as ethnicity, diversity, and psychological factors. This research uses family role as moderator. Other variable may be used as moderators, like an innovative environment, supportive supervisor in future.

In our research, here are some limitations. First, our study sample was gathered from the public sector universities in Narowal. Hence, the sample size limited the findings' generalizability to the larger population. Second, time constraints limit the breadth and depth because there was a short period. Third, this study is cross-sectional due to time and financial constraints. Longitudinal studies in the same context may provide more in-depth results related to career adaptability and sustainability among university students.

References:

- Akanni, A. A., & Oduaran, C. A. (2018). Perceived social support and life satisfaction among freshmen: Mediating roles of academic self-efficacy and academic adjustment. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 28(2), 89-93.
- Avram, E., Burtaverde, V., & Zanzfirescu, A.-Ş. (2019). The incremental validity of career adaptability in predicting academic performance. *Social Psychology of Education*, 22(4), 867-882.
- Bandura, A. (1978). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Advances in behaviour research and therapy*, 1(4), 139-161.
- Bi, X., & Wang, S. (2021). Parent-adolescent communication quality and life satisfaction: The mediating roles of autonomy and future orientation.

- Psychology Research and Behavior Management, 14, 1091.
- Journal of management information systems, 18(1), 185-214.
- Chen, C., Shen, H., & Li, X. (2009). Reliability and validity of adult dispositional hope scale. *Chinese Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 17(1), 24-26.
- Cohen, J. (1988). Set correlation and contingency tables. *Applied psychological measurement*, 12(4), 425-434.
- De Hauw, S., & Greenhaus, J. H. (2015). Building a sustainable career: The role of work-home balance in career decision making. In *Handbook of research on sustainable careers*: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- De Vos, A., Van der Heijden, B. I., & Akkermans, J. (2020). Sustainable careers: Towards a conceptual model. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 117, 103196.
- Di Maggio, I., Santilli, S., Ginevra, M., Nota, L., & Soresi, S. (2018). *The assessment instruments of the project Stay passionate, courageous, inclusive, sustainable, etc.*. Paper presented at the Poster Session Presented at XVIII SIO Conference.
- Diener, E., Suh, E. M., Lucas, R. E., & Smith, H. L. (1999). Subjective well-being: Three decades of progress. *Psychological bulletin*, 125(2), 276.
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of marketing research*, 18(1), 39-50.
- Gallup, I. (2022). State of the global workplace report. *Gallup.com*. Retrieved July, 21, 2022.
- Gilman, R., & Huebner, S. (2003). A review of life satisfaction research with children and adolescents. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 18(2), 192.
- Ginevra, M. C., Pallini, S., Vecchio, G. M., Nota, L., & Soresi, S. (2016). Future orientation and attitudes mediate career adaptability and decidedness. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 95, 102-110.
- Gold, A. H., Malhotra, A., & Segars, A. H. (2001). Knowledge management: An organizational capabilities perspective.
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Kossek, E. E. (2014). The contemporary career: A work-home perspective. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 1(1), 361-388.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (2010). SEM: An introduction. *Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective*, 5(6), 629-686.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An emerging tool in business research. *European business review*, 26(2), 106-121.
- Hayes, A. F. (2009). Beyond Baron and Kenny: Statistical mediation analysis in the new millennium. *Communication monographs*, 76(4), 408-420.
- Henseler, J., & Fassott, G. (2010). Testing moderating effects in PLS path models: An illustration of available procedures. *Handbook of partial least squares: Concepts, methods and applications*, 713-735.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 43, 115-135.
- Hirschi, A. (2009). Career adaptability development in adolescence: Multiple predictors and effect on sense of power and life satisfaction. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 74(2), 145-155.
- Hirschi, A., Herrmann, A., & Keller, A. C. (2015). Career adaptivity, adaptability, and adapting: A conceptual and empirical investigation. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 87, 1-10.
- Johnston, C. S. (2018). A systematic review of the career adaptability literature and future outlook. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 26(1), 3-30.
- Joseph F, H. (2016). Multivariate data analysis: An overview. *International encyclopedia of statistical science*, 904-907.

- Kline, R. B. (2011). Convergence of structural equation modeling and multilevel modeling. *The SAGE handbook of innovation in social research methods*, 562-589.
- Lawrence, B., Hall, D., Arthur, M., De Vos, A., & Van der Heijden, B. (2015). Handbook of Research on Sustainable Careers. In.
- Liang, Y. (2000). Study on achievement goals, attribution styles and academic self-efficacy of college students. *Central China Normal University*, 32.
- Pavot, W., & Diener, E. (1993). The affective and cognitive context of self-reported measures of subjective well-being. *Social indicators research*, 28, 1-20.
- Pintrich, P. R., & De Groot, E. V. (1990). Motivational and self-regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. *Journal of educational psychology*, 82(1), 33.
- Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F. (2008). Asymptotic and resampling strategies for assessing and comparing indirect effects in multiple mediator models. *Behavior research methods*, 40(3), 879-891.
- Rigdon, E., Schumacker, R., Wothke, W., & Marcoulides, G. (1998). Interaction and nonlinear effects in structural equation modeling. In: Erlbaum, Mahwah, NJ.
- Santilli, S., Marcionetti, J., Rochat, S., Rossier, J., & Nota, L. (2017). Career adaptability, hope, optimism, and life satisfaction in Italian and Swiss adolescents. *Journal of Career Development*, 44(1), 62-76.
- Santilli, S., Nota, L., Ginevra, M. C., & Soresi, S. (2014). Career adaptability, hope and life satisfaction in workers with intellectual disability. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 85(1), 67-74.
- Savickas, M. L. (2005). The theory and practice of career construction. *Career development and counseling: Putting theory and research to work*, 1, 42-70.
- Savickas, M. L., & Porfeli, E. J. (2012). Career Adapt-Abilities Scale: Construction, reliability, and measurement equivalence across 13 countries. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 80(3), 661-673.
- Scioli, A., Chamberlin, C. M., Samor, C. M., Lapointe, A. B., Campbell, T. L., Macleod, A. R., & McLenon, J. (1997). A prospective study of hope, optimism, and health. *Psychological Reports*, 81(3), 723-733.
- Snyder, C. R. (2002). Hope theory: Rainbows in the mind. *Psychological inquiry*, 13(4), 249-275.
- Staats, S. (1989). Hope: A comparison of two self-report measures for adults. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 53(2), 366-375.
- Strauss, K., Griffin, M. A., & Parker, S. K. (2012). Future work selves: how salient hoped-for identities motivate proactive career behaviors. *Journal of applied psychology*, 97(3), 580.
- Suen, H.-Y., Chen, M. Y.-C., & Lu, S.-H. (2019). Does the use of synchrony and artificial intelligence in video interviews affect interview ratings and applicant attitudes? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 98, 93-101.
- Taber, B. J., & Blankemeyer, M. (2015). Future work self and career adaptability in the prediction of proactive career behaviors. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 86, 20-27.
- Tolentino, L. R., Garcia, P. R. J. M., Lu, V. N., Restubog, S. L. D., Bordia, P., & Plewa, C. (2014). Career adaptation: The relation of adaptability to goal orientation, proactive personality, and career optimism. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 84(1), 39-48.
- Tordera, N., Peiro, J. M., Ayala, Y., Villajos, E., & Truxillo, D. (2020). The lagged influence of organizations' human resources practices on employees' career sustainability: The moderating role of age. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 120, 103444.
- Uddin, M., & Bhuiyan, A. (2019). Development of the family support scale (FSS) for elderly people. *MOJ Gerontology and Geriatrics*, 4(1), 17-20.
- van den Groenendaal, S. M. E., Akkermans, J., Fleisher, C., Kooij, D. T., Poell, R. F., & Freese, C. (2022). A qualitative exploration of solo self-employed workers' career sustainability. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 134, 103692.

- Vinzi, V. E., Chin, W. W., Henseler, J., & Wang, H. (2010). *Handbook of partial least squares* (Vol. 201): Springer.
- Watson, D., Clark, L. A., Weber, K., Assenheimer, J. S., Strauss, M. E., & McCormick, R. A. (1995). Testing a tripartite model: II. Exploring the symptom structure of anxiety and depression in student, adult, and patient samples. *Journal of abnormal Psychology*, 104(1), 15.
- Watts, R. J., Diemer, M. A., & Voight, A. M. (2011). Critical consciousness: Current status and future directions. *New directions for child and adolescent development*, 2011(134), 43-57.
- Wilkins-Yel, K. G., Roach, C. M., Tracey, T. J., & Yel, N. (2018). The effects of career adaptability on intended academic persistence: The mediating role of academic satisfaction. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 108, 67-77.
- Williams, L. J., & Anderson, S. E. (1991). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment as predictors of organizational citizenship and in-role behaviors. *Journal of management*, 17(3), 601-617.
- Yang, H.-L., & Lin, C.-L. (2014). Why do people stick to Facebook web site? A value theory-based view. *Information Technology & People*, 27(1), 21-37.
- Young, R. A. (1983). Career development of adolescents: An ecological perspective. *Journal of Youth and adolescence*, 12(5), 401-417.
- Zeinalipour, H. (2021). School connectedness, academic self-efficacy, and academic performance: mediating role of hope. *Psychological Reports*, 00332941211006926.
- Zeng, Q., He, Y., Li, J., Liang, Z., Zhang, M., Yi, D., & Quan, J. (2022). Hope, future work self and life satisfaction among vocational high school students in China: The roles of career adaptability and academic self-efficacy. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 199, 111822.
- Zhang, Liguo, H., & Xue, Z. (2004). Adolescent students' life satisfaction: its construct and scale development. *PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCE-SHANGHAI*, 27(5; ISSU 151), 1257-1260.